

MANAGERIAL COACHING IMPACT ON GEN Z'S INNOVATIVE BEHAVIORS AT KNOWLEDGE-BASED FIRMS IN EMERGING ECONOMIES

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ABSTRACT

The subject of coaching within organizations has been attracting intense attention from HR professionals and researchers over recent decades. Workplace coaching by line managers towards their staff (aka managerial coaching – abbreviated as MC) is believed to bring numerous benefits to organizations at individual levels, such as empowering employees, improving their individual performance or motivating them to excel etc. Meanwhile, another research topic that has triggered a lot of study from researchers and practitioners is employees' innovative work behavior (IWB) which is the ability to continuously innovate and improve products, services and work processes. However, little previous empirical study on the association between MC and IWB has been previously conducted.

This study is aimed at understanding how MC is associated with IWB at knowledge-based consulting firms in emerging markets via biographical and focus group interview qualitative research methods.

INTRODUCTION

Coaching refers to “the managerial activity of creating, by communication only, the climate, environment, and context that empowers individuals and teams to generate results” (Evered, 1989). Meanwhile the Worldwide Association of Business Coaches (2007) stated “Business coaching is the process of engaging in meaningful communication with individuals in businesses, organizations, institutions or governments, with the goal of promoting success at all levels of the organizations by affecting the actions of those individuals”. “Coaching in organizations” (Homan & Miller, 2008) shared that coaching leadership is highly common

in today's workplace as "its positive nature promotes development of new skills, revisits company objectives and fosters a confident company culture."

According to (Schroth, 2019), more and more is being expected of modern managers. Among key traits of successful managers, workplace coaching is a one-on-one, custom-tailored learning and development process that uses a collaborative, reflective, goal-focused relationship to achieve professional outcomes that are valued by the coachee. Especially many organizations realize that managers need not only technical expertise but important soft skills, among which coaching has been found to provide emotional support and to reduce stress of employees. Coaching can effectively help in goal attainment as well as increased psychological and workplace well-being of the workforce.

On a different aspect, both managers and leaders are supposed to be positive role models in their areas of responsibility or competence so that their employees can look up to them and be encouraged to perform well. Managers who are good at leading and encouraging their staff, recognizing and respecting their efforts and hard work, and especially being the reflection of trustworthy individuals and outstanding at generating trust, are effective role models. Especially, they must live with honesty and accountability, and become individuals who have their employees' best interests at heart. (2021, 2022, LinkedIn).

Another organizational citizenship behavior that has been the strong focus of study by both elite professionals and researchers is employees' innovative work behavior. At both organizational and individual levels, innovation plays a critical role to the organization's success (Lynn K. Mytelka, 2002). At organizational level, there has been increasing interest in finding ways to ignite employees' innovative behaviors. In addressing that objective, the role of managers in impacting employee's innovative behavior has received a lot of attention from researchers and practitioners alike worldwide.

Via practical coaching activities at intense knowledge-based firms in three emerging markets, namely Vietnam, Thailand and Malaysia, the researcher aims to explore the impact of managers' coaching on Gen Z employees' innovative work behaviors. The research is expected to contribute significantly in terms of managerial contributions to the company management, especially the HR professionals, on developing a coaching culture across the company, with focus on mid-level managers via improving their coaching ability.

This paper is aimed at answering the below two questions:

1. *Is there any positive association between managers' coaching (MC) and employee's innovative behavior (IWB)?*
2. *What factors may impact the relationship between MC and IWB?*

LITERATURE REVIEW

WORKPLACE COACHING AND ITS BENEFITS

The topic of coaching has been receiving more and more attention and interest from both coaching practitioners, human resources professionals and the world of work in general. Especially the past two decades have seen a significant increase in interest in executive and workplace coaching. Regarding the latter coaching, with several benefits to organizations such as empowering individuals to take responsibility and understand their strengths as well as weaknesses for self-improvement and self-development, coaching has moved from being the latest management trend to a mainstream driver of organizations' development and talent management (Cavanagh, 2007). Effective workplace coaching is also said to improve individual performance, help identify and develop high potential employees. Other benefits of workplace coaching include motivating and empowering individuals to excel etc.

The first applications of psychological theory and practice to coaching (in particular, athletic coaching) can be traced to the 1920s. Since then, coaching has evolved into several forms: life coaching, executive coaching and especially workplace coaching. Coaching activities in organizations are believed to contribute to creating a coaching culture (Cavanagh, 2007). Together with coaching culture across the organization, numerous benefits of coaching to the organizations have been reported like leading to employees' higher motivation, engagement, greater productivity, and employee retention. Notably, coaching is said to unlock a person's potential and maximize their own performance. Also coaching as an adaptive methodology can be useful in navigating local and global complexities and creating opportunities for new thinking and behaviors (Whybrow, 2021).

MANAGERS' POSITIVE ROLE MODEL

A role model is someone that others, particularly younger people, can copy in terms of their actions, success, or example. The father of this theory is the sociologist Robert K. Merton (1910 – 2003) who is credited with coining the term "role model". According to his theory, people compare themselves to reference groups of people who hold the social role they admire, for example young generation often idolize and imitate celebrities or professional athletes.

Role models are crucial in the workplace because they contribute to boosting employee morale, fostering a positive work atmosphere, improving communication, motivating others, and promoting healthy rivalry. In this research context of innovation study, good role model managers are expected to live the value of innovation as part of their nature.

INITIATIVE-TAKING SKILL VS CREATIVITY SKILL

Initiative-taking skill refers to the ability to independently identify and act upon opportunities, challenges, or problems without being prompted or directed by others. The ability to take initiatives can lead to innovation and “there are actions that leaders can take to encourage such personal initiative, including focusing more on the act of taking initiative than on the possible outcome” (Frohman, 2017). Meanwhile creativity skill involves generating unique and original ideas, concepts, or solutions by making connections between seemingly unrelated concepts or by thinking outside the box and “in order to be considered creative, the product or an idea must be different from what has been done before” (Amabile, 1996).

INNOVATION AT WORKPLACE

Another topic that has drawn special attention of researchers and practitioners is employees' innovative behavior which is defined as the intentional proposal and application of novel and improved ideas, processes, practices, and policies aimed at organizational effectiveness, business success, and long-term sustainability. Quite different from creativity, which pinpoints the novelty and radicalness of ideas, innovative behavior is concerned more about the execution and realization of ideas (Neil Anderson, 2014).

Innovative work behavior (IWB) in the workplace is described as complex behaviour consisting of a set of three different behavioral tasks: idea generation, idea promotion, and idea realization. Individual innovation begins with idea generation, that is, the production of novel and useful ideas in any domain (Janssen, 2000).

In the studies on employee engagement, innovative behavior is often discussed as part of job performance, which is generally broken down into two types—in-role and extra-role performance. In-role performance refers to formally prescribed behaviors and outcomes as part of an incumbent's work requirements, while extra-role performance refers to discretionary behaviors that enrich an organization's functioning but may not be formally rewarded or sanctioned by the organization (Christian, 2011). However, recent studies using the JD-R (Job demand) (Kibum Kwon, 2019) model have reconsidered this classification. They argue that innovative behavior is a type of performance distinguished from either in-role or extra-role performance because it goes beyond prescribed requirements. According to Rodríguez-Sánchez (2017) team creativity is in part inspired by the motivational theories of the Job Demands–Resources model (Rodríguez-Sánchez, 2017). According to West & Farr (1990) (Michael A West, 1990) team creativity should be differentiated from team innovation in the sense that creativity refers to the idea generation stage, while innovation also implies the introduction and application within a team of ideas, processes, products, or procedures that are new to the team

and are designed to be useful. However, challenging the status quo and thinking outside of the box might not be explicit in a job description, but are tacit norms required of employers in today's workplace.

GEN Z EMPLOYEES' ROLE IN GLOBAL WORKFORCE

The setting of this research is intense knowledge-based consulting environment with the dominant representation of Gen Z employees, those born in 1997 - 2012. These are the most important labor making about 30% of the global workforce by 2025 (Mărginean, 2021). Unlike their predecessors, Gen Z are primarily focused on flexibility, personalization and emotional support and have been found to be the most achievement-oriented of the generations (Schroth, 2019). They also prefer in-person interactions, embrace change and highly competitive. They wish to be mentored at work and are well aware that success must come with career-long learning (Mărginean, 2021). In the workplace they have a strong desire for recognition of their work too.

A report published by Workforce Institute shows that they seek trust and support in a manager above any other managerial quality. Gen Z prefers collaborative learning than a "telling" approach, and this would be successful only when the managers relate to employees in such a way that maximizes their engagement, well-being, and performance (Schroth, 2019). Those are special traits that managers need to pay special attention to enable the best results in working with Gen Z.

Meanwhile, in organizations, coaching by managers is said to empower individual's potential, improve their performance and initiative taking ability, those qualities that may positively lead to IWB. With reference to the previous studies, the paper focuses on studying the initiative taking skill of Gen Zers that lead to their IWB. The researcher also identifies the positive role model of managers that moderates this MC – IWB relationship.

THE GROW MODEL BY WHITMORE

This paper is based on a number of theories. The first one is the GROW model by **(Goals – Reality – Options – Way forward)** (Whitmore, *Coaching: An International Journal of Theory, Research and Practice*, 2009). According to Whitmore (2009), the GROW model helps to solve problems and achieve goals because it is a solution-focused model. The four stages in the model help the coach to captivate the coachee's interest. The four distinct stages were represented by a series of questions to help develop people and discover their potential. It is an ideal model for setting goals, solving problems, preserving personal achievement, and efficiency. Firstly, the coach and the coachee need to establish the goals of coaching as it is compulsory to align on the goals before both parties can start

their coaching sessions. At the same time, goals must be SMART: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time-bound. The main question to be addressed when setting goals is whether or not they fit the overall objectives.

The last step of the GROW coaching model is the choice of one option from the various options stated. Then, the choice is transformed into a more concrete plan. After a well-planned strategy, the coachee's motivation to follow this plan is maximized. The last phase involves converting the discussions into decisions by means of taking specific actions to move forward (Grant, 2022). In this paper, Table 1 presents the whole process of GROW model where the coach should help the coachee to move from their current positions towards greater effectiveness and motivation. The assumption is that, if questions in each stage are properly dealt with, obstacles that may negatively impact the individual's performance will be reduced (de Haan & Kasozi, 2015). One of the most critical roles of a coach is to guide his/her coachee to improve their performance by helping the coachee to make better decisions, solve problems that are holding them back. Coaches also helps the coachees to acquire new skills and doing things differently, and subsequently, they can progress their careers.

The idea of setting goals is strongly related to the goal-setting theory of motivation by Edwin Locke (Locke, 1991), which advocates the setting of clear, specific and challenging goals as this leads to clear direction and motivation. The second stage is the reality in which the coachee will explain the current reality and what is wrong to help them to see why change is necessary (Weinstein, 2013). It is essential for both the parties to know the current situation because the argument is that it is difficult for them to solve the problem if they do not have a clear picture of the anticipated destination (Henry Kimsey-House, 2011; Whitworth, 2007).

According to Bridges and Bridges (2017), people cannot solve problems they do not understand or reach goals without considering the starting point (Bridges & Bridges, 2017). As a coach, the crucial role is to stimulate coachees' self-evaluation and identify the obstacles that have been holding them back. This is the critical part where the coach needs to summarize and repeat what he or she understands with regard to the actual situation of the coachee. The option stage is to generate ideas that can contribute to the solution of the problem. It involves exploring into various options and focusing not only on the right answers but on several alternatives to have as many options as possible so that specific action steps can be selected.

Table 1: The GROW Model.

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Example Questions</i>
G – Goal	Coachee is asked to clarify what they want to achieve from each session. Determines the focus of coaching.	What do you want to achieve this session? How would you like to feel afterwards? What would be the best use of this time?
R – Reality	Raise awareness of present realities. Examine how current situation is impacting coachee's goals.	How have things gone in the past week? How have you handled any problems? What worked? What didn't work?
O – Options	Identify and assess available options. Encourage solution-focused thinking and brainstorming.	What possible options do you have? What has worked for you in the past? What haven't you tried yet that might work?
W - Wrap-Up	Assists the coachee determine next steps. Develops an action plan and builds motivation.	What is the most important thing to do next? What might get in the way? Who might be able to support you? How will you feel when this is done?

Sources: Grant & Greene, 2004; Landsberg, 1997; Spence & Grant, 2007; Whitmore, 1992.

FOUR-FACTOR THEORY OF TEAM CLIMATE FOR INNOVATION

According to Anderson and West (1990), there are four team climate factors that facilitate innovation: vision, participative safety, task orientation, and support for innovation. Accordingly, “Innovation is enhanced if (a) vision is understandable, valued, and accepted by the team members; (b) team members perceive they can propose new ideas and solutions without being judged or criticized; (c) there is a stimulating debate and discussion of different possible solutions within the team which at the same time will more likely be carefully examined; and finally (d) team members perceive support for innovation (A, 1990).

The researcher hypothesizes that to successfully ignite IWB of employees, their organizations must be equipped with innovation levers or enablers, within which the employees are encouraged to make good initiatives by themselves (options in the GROW model). In other words, the ability to produce good or even great initiatives are called the initiative taking skill, which according to top global consulting firms, is the prerequisite for staff to come to IWB. Initiative taking skill is also one of the most sought after skills by today employers.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK & RESEARCH METHOD

Based on the above theories, the researcher has proposed the conceptual framework below.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The researcher has four propositions as identified themes below before she conducts a two-phase qualitative research:

Proposition 1: The managers with coaching practice (managerial coaching) can positively ignite their employees' initiative taking skill

Proposition 2: The positive role model of a manager plays a positive influence on the initiative taking skill of his/her employee(s)

Proposition 3: The initiative taking skill of employees positively associates with their innovative work behavior

Proposition 4: Innovation enablers/factors impacts the relations between initiative taking skill of employees and their innovative work behavior.

This researcher aims to carry out her study in three phases:

Phase 1 (Descriptive analysis): By using biographical approach, the researcher will select and study the most suitable respondents, who are broken down in two groups, the 1st group comprises six legendary coaching managers among the three chosen countries and the 2nd group is consisted of twelve coachees who are their employees. That means each selected coach introduces 2 coachees for the researcher's focus group interviews that follow.

Timeline: July 2023

Phase 2 (In-depth analysis): A qualitative research via concept-driven, content analysis approach is carried out. Via the GROW model, literature review on workplace coaching and semi-structured interviews, the researcher has identified 4 themes that can later developed into 12 - 15 categories. The identified categories will be next discussed in depth between the author and the interviewees from which more sub-categories were identified.

Timeline: August 2023

Format: Zoom-based interviews

Theme 1: Coaching impacts on employees' initiative taking skill

Theme 2: Influence of managers' role model on employees' initiative taking skill

Theme 3: Relation of employees' initiative taking skill with their innovative work behavior

Theme 4: Innovation factors' association with employees' innovative work behavior

Phase 3 (Special Study and ATC writing)

Timeline: September 2023

Finalization of SS and ATC in **October 2023**

Due to geographical challenges, the researcher uses Zoom platform for conducting online focus group interviews (web conferencing interviews). Audio-recorded using Zoom audio-record feature and a back-up recorder are used. Despite limited results as compared to direct onsite interviews, this web conferencing interviews on Zoom can produce a number of benefits that are quite satisfactory for research purposes:

- * Geographically diverse sample of participants thanks to Zoom-based focus group interviews
- * Diversity of perspective (not obtained in one geographic location or in-person focus group)
- * Mirror in-person conversations where participants can effectively converse with one person speaking at a time, thus can create similar high-quality data.

THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS

Despite lots of research on IWB over decades and previous studies have found several of its antecedents such as transformational leadership (Bilal Afsar, Yuosre F. Badir, 2014), knowledge-based HRM practices and so on, there has

been little empirical study on MC as an antecedent of IWB. Therefore, from theoretical contributions, the paper will contribute to bridge the current gap in literature review of how coaching competence of managers will contribute to employees' innovative behaviors.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Managers at organizations are applying coaching as a sustainable way to develop their employees' potential and optimize their IWB. As the above literature review mentions, employees should be the one to decide their actions to take via thinking thoroughly to answer their coach's questions on the GROW model. Mentoring in this regard does not help them as they tend to forget what other people (their managers) tell them to do, but they can hardly forget what they commit or have a solid plan to execute. Coaching has thus become an effective, important management tool to help the leaders and managers develop their employees successfully and ignite their innovative behavior.

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